

**The Impact of Financial Education on the Financial Literacy of American High-Schoolers:
An Analysis**

Katherine Manuel

Department of Economics, Macalester College

ECON294: Economics of the Twin Cities

Professor Sarah West

December 16th, 2023

Author Note

Katherine Manuel, Macalester College

Abstract

In this paper, Manuel evaluates the relationship between financial education and financial literacy in an attempt to predict the efficacy of recent changes to Minnesota's educational policy. Using the economic theory of diminishing marginal returns and considering human interest, she theorizes the different potential outcomes of financial education courses on the financial literacy of American high schoolers. She then turns to the existing key literature on this relationship, evaluating the quality and accuracy of their research, before determining that the existing data is inconclusive and further research will need to be conducted for a definitive conclusion.

The Impact of Financial Education on the Financial Literacy of American High-Schoolers: An Analysis

Introduction

Within the past few months, the Minnesota state government officially announced guaranteed and required personal financial education classes for Minnesota high school students as soon as the 2024-2025 school year (Faircloth, 2023). In this paper, “financial education” refers specifically to informational, educational courses in high schools that aim to bolster students’ financial literacy. In turn, “financial literacy” will henceforth refer to one’s understanding of personal finance topics, including but not limited to personal investments, home ownership, and debt management. These new classes are part of a larger series of educational reforms within Minnesota, with the state’s educational policy being updated to include changes such as limiting student expulsion in elementary schools and requiring schools to provide menstrual products for students in need, between the grades of four and twelve (Griffith, 2023). However, for the sake of clarity, the specific reform of the financial literacy classes will be focused on in this paper. For local community members such as Anita Drentlaw, the current CEO of New Market Bank, the change is a welcome one – they believe that as the students grow and take on financial responsibility, financial literacy becomes increasingly imperative (Severson, 2023). Currently, financial literacy classes are rare: a study by Next Gen Personal Finance (NGPF) found that only 8.1% of Minnesotan students were guaranteed to take a financial literacy course before their graduation before the policy change (NGPF, 2023). To emphasize the change’s importance, it is imperative to note that in a 2019 Everfi study, 53% of *college* students in America stated that out of their current concerns, they were the “least prepared” in money management (Zapp, 2019).

In terms of funding, the financial literacy classes are part of HF2497 – a bill dedicated to managing educational funding within Minnesota that received much of its funding from Minnesota’s \$17.6 billion budget surplus (Abrams, 2023). As of May, HF2497 requires \$23.2 billion within the next two years, with some of the money also coming from a reallocation of funds previously for the “English Learner cross-subsidy” (Abrams, 2023). The English Learner cross-subsidy is money from the government used to help support costs for English learning programs within the state (MREA, 2022). With policymakers having a clear idea of where the funding will come from, individuals such as Dr. Julie Bunn, the Executive Director of the Minnesota Council on Economic Education (MCEE), applaud the state government’s efforts to make financial literacy more equitable and accessible (NGPF 2023). By making guaranteed courses in personal finance more accessible to students across the state, regardless of school location or ranking, policymakers hope to equip their young populace with the skills necessary to make wise financial decisions. This desired effect is of extreme importance, especially when understanding racial economic disparities still plague the state – in 2018, 33.8% of Indigenous Americans were below the poverty line, compared to 7.4% of the White population (Macht, 2018). As such, the need for equal access to guaranteed financial literacy courses is made all the more necessary.

Delving deeper into potential policy outcomes, one could expect more significant effects if students were not exposed to financial education before taking these courses. The economic theory of diminishing marginal returns states that as the amount of input increases past a certain level, the amount of output produced will slowly decline for each additional unit of input. In terms of education, test score analysis can reveal diminishing marginal returns to knowledge. Students with low initial test scores can expect significant academic gains over time (in

comparison to students with high initial test scores) (Driscoll et al., 2007). Solely understanding this theory, one might expect this financial literacy policy to have the greatest effects on high school students without any prior financial education. Inversely, the policy would be expected to have less-significant effects on students who have already been exposed to some form of financial literacy (either through speaking with friends and family, personal research, and the like). I hypothesize that evaluating the economic theory of diminishing marginal returns and accounting for human interest, one would expect this financial education policy to have the most significant effects on students who are interested in financial literacy, regardless of prior financial literacy knowledge.

Throughout this paper, the policy and its potential effects will be reviewed in greater detail by evaluating the relationship between financial education and financial literacy. In the “History” section, a brief history of past educational reforms and economic statistics in Minnesota will be shared. In the “Theory” section, the scale and direction of the policy’s outcomes will be estimated using the economic theory of diminishing marginal returns in relation to prior financial literacy knowledge and considering human interest. In the “Estimation Challenges” section, many potential empirical challenges of measuring this policy’s outcomes will be explored. In the “Empirical Literature Review” section, key empirical literature and research on the relationship between financial education and financial literacy will be analyzed and critiqued with the aforementioned estimation challenges taken into account. After the policy’s main estimated outcomes have been explained in depth and the existing literature reviewed, recommendations for further, future studies will be shared.

History

Within the past decades, the Minnesota state government has implemented several other reforms impacting the state's public schools. Two examples are promoting investigation of child maltreatment claims in public schools, daycares, and residential facilities in 1999 and numerous desegregation policy improvements in the 1970s and 1990s (Sullivan, 2000). In 1996, three years prior to the child maltreatment reform of 1999, there were 10,200 victims of child maltreatment in Minnesota (U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, 1998). In comparison, in 2005, six years afterward, there were 8,499 victims (U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, 2007). Since the passing of this child maltreatment reform, the number of child maltreatment victims had decreased by over a thousand within the span of nine years. However, in comparison to this success, reforms such as the desegregation policy improvements were not as effective. Though the state has attempted to promote equity and desegregation for decades, segregation in Minnesota schools has considerably worsened. Since the 1990s, the amount of segregated schools within the state has significantly increased. In 1993, 0.8% of Black students attended schools in which 90% or more of the students were people of color – in comparison, this number was 25.7% in 2018 (Einhorn & Chiwaya, 2020). Understanding these two cases, it is clear that Minnesota's public school reforms have achieved varying success. However, while both examples are attempts to further improve state schools, it is also significant to note that they aim to do so in extremely different ways, making comparative analyses of their effectiveness difficult. Similarly, it is also difficult to compare these two cases to the newly implemented financial education courses, as all reforms differ in their manner of attempting improvement.

Aside from relating Minnesota's new financial education courses to past state reforms, one could also imagine that these courses would experience greater success if tailored to the

specific needs of Minnesota's residents. Specifically, while Minnesotans boasted the highest average credit score out of all American states in 2023, Minnesota is also one of the highest-ranking states in terms of the percentage of college students who are graduating with debt (Kim, 2023; Minnesota Education Equity Partnership, 2023). Should the proper officials take into account these needs when deciding on financial education curriculums, perhaps these guaranteed and required courses would have more significant effects on students. In this way, if the reforms focus on Minnesota-specific issues, any success the financial education classes experience will be amplified. However, at this point in time, any conversations regarding curriculum are conjecture at best, as information regarding course content has yet to become publicly available.

Theory

Solely concerning diminishing marginal returns, this financial education policy might bring forth the most significant increases in financial literacy in students with no prior financial knowledge. As revealed in Figure 1 below, increases in input will result in increases in output only to a certain point – the Point of Maximum Output. Looking at input and output, students starting with no hours spent learning (no prior knowledge) would experience greater increases in financial literacy than those who started with more hours spent learning (more prior knowledge). Students with limited or no prior knowledge would be placed around the L1 point, while students with prior knowledge would be around L3. The students with prior knowledge would therefore be past the Point of Diminishing Returns, and would experience decreases to their marginal output (increases in their financial literacy test scores) more significantly than those without prior knowledge. As such, one might expect this financial education policy to have the greatest

effects on students with no prior financial literacy, as they would not experience diminishing marginal returns as significantly as students with prior financial knowledge.

Figure 1

Financial Literacy Test Scores by Hours Spent Learning

Note. Created by Katherine Manuel

However, one economic theory can only take us so far. Prior studies researching the impact of financial education on financial literacy have revealed several factors that must be considered to accurately measure this relationship. Examples include student demographics, how financial literacy is measured, and the methods used to implement the financial education curriculum in the classroom. Because financial education is a broad topic, encompassing different curriculums, it is extremely difficult to measure how significantly it impacts high school students' financial literacy. Human interest must also be taken into consideration – herein lies the second vital element influencing financial literacy outcomes.

While diminishing marginal returns theory allows for impersonal prediction, human interest is not always as clear – in many cases, prior knowledge and diminishing marginal returns may not have as significant an impact on the effectiveness of this financial literacy policy as initially hypothesized. In simply considering the theory of diminishing marginal returns, one conditional statement is clear: if students come in with no prior financial knowledge, they will experience more significant gains to financial literacy from financial education. However, the inclusion of human interest considers whether students even care about the material being taught. As such, I now propose another conditional statement regarding this theory: if students are interested in becoming more financially literate, then they will experience more significant benefits from financial education. Past studies have hypothesized that younger high school students, namely freshmen and sophomores, lack the foresight and exposure to have a motivated interest in making the most of their financial education and becoming more financially literate, regardless of their prior financial knowledge (Mandell, 2008). One could therefore expect all younger high school students to perform relatively similarly on financial literacy exams after taking a financial education course, regardless of prior knowledge. While students with prior financial knowledge might perform marginally better, these students are still young, with limited opportunities to practice financial literacy in supplementary real-world situations. As such, one might predict any differences in performance between those with prior knowledge and those without to not be statistically significant.

Considering the difference in effectiveness of this financial education policy between students with and without prior knowledge concerning the theory of diminishing marginal returns also assumes that such prior knowledge is accurate and sufficient enough in amount to matter. Consider, now, a hypothetical situation: two high school students exhibit similar interests

in becoming financially literate. However, one of the students has parents who are world-renowned financial educators, while the other student's parents work in careers unrelated to finance and education. In this scenario, the student with the financial educators as parents would probably learn much less from this policy's financial education than the other student, due to the economic law of diminishing marginal returns. However, the reality of the matter is a stark difference: a 2001 survey revealed that a very small minority of parents felt that they were "very effective" at financially educating their children (Varcoe et al., 2005). As such, regardless of interest, the groups of students with and without prior knowledge may be closer in input than originally anticipated. Again considering the previous graph, students without knowledge may still be at point L1. However, students with prior knowledge might be closer to point L1 than L3, as previously stated. In this case, it would make sense for students with and without prior knowledge to have similar test scores after undergoing financial education, as they started from levels of financial knowledge more similar than initially assumed.

However, regardless of diminishing marginal returns theory and human interest, any hypotheses regarding the effects of financial education on financial literacy heavily depend on the accuracy of existing literature. If we assume that the existing literature on the relationship between financial education and financial literacy properly accounts for estimation challenges and provides accurate findings, then we can make accurate assumptions regarding this relationship. If the key papers evaluated within the "Empirical Literature Review" section properly account for the estimation challenges that will be revealed in the following section, it would be relatively safe to assume that this paper could properly evaluate the relationship between financial education and financial literacy, and determine under which specific conditions my hypothesis will be supported. However, if such key papers prove to be unreliable

in their research or reveal difficulties in analyzing this relationship, further sufficient evidence will be required to come to a set conclusion.

Taking into consideration the economic theory of diminishing marginal returns, human interest, the meaning of what constitutes “prior knowledge” in high school students, and the importance of accurate research findings, three primary conditional statements can be reviewed: If human interest is not taken into account, then the theory of diminishing marginal returns will explain that students with no prior knowledge will experience greater returns to financial literacy than students with prior knowledge. If human interest *is* taken into account, students who are interested in financial literacy will benefit more significantly from financial education than those who are not, regardless of prior knowledge. If the key existing literature on the relationship between financial education and financial literacy properly accounts for estimation challenges and provides accurate results, this paper can come to a proper conclusion measuring the effects of Minnesota’s recent financial education policy.

Estimation Challenges

When analyzing the relationship between financial literacy and the policy’s financial education courses, several estimation challenges must be addressed. The measurement of financial education’s impact on financial literacy is heavily dependent on changes in people. As such, there are many demographic challenges – differences in income levels, race, sex, age, location, and employment between class groups being particularly notable. Because the related research and studies deal with the educational and personal growth of people, these demographic differences are extremely important to consider – socioeconomic disparities within these groups may overstate or understate the impact of financial education on financial literacy if not properly accounted for. In an attempt to address this, studies such as that of Mandell have separated

student data and findings based on demographic data such as parents' income and education, sex, race, and regional location (Mandell, 2008).

Another challenge is how financial literacy is measured. As previously stated, pre-tests and post-tests (taken before and after participation in the related financial education course, respectively) can be used to determine financial literacy. However, whether these tests consist of true/false, multiple choice, or open-ended questions can impact findings. Open-ended questions can more accurately depict complex, written comprehension of financial concepts, but can be difficult to quantify due to their subjective nature. True/false and multiple choice questions are easier to quantify, but there is also the chance that students are guessing some of their answers, leading to an overstatement of their financial literacy. Additionally, researchers may choose to forgo tests entirely, evaluating the impact of financial education on financial literacy in the long term and tracking the financial habits of students years after course completion. Question type might overstate gains to financial literacy, but measurement differences may make it near-impossible to accurately determine any gains at all between studies. In an attempt to address this challenge, not much can be done, except instating formal, shared research methods. For data simplification, many researchers focus on a specific question type and temporal scope when conducting their research. For Walstad et al.'s study, multiple choice questions were used, allowing data more quantifiable than open-ended questions and less subject to change than true/false questions (Walstad et al., 2010). While such focuses are achievable for individual studies, differences in measurement between studies may prove to be problematic when analyzing multiple.

Differences between schools studied also prove to be a potent estimation challenge. When comparing classes within and between school systems, teacher preparation and course

content are fated to be different. Some school systems may have better-trained teachers than others, and there may be differences in content within the financial education courses being taught. These differences would undoubtedly be reflected in student scores on post-tests as a result of their class experiences. Depending on teacher skill and course content, the impacts of financial education on financial literacy may be overstated or understated – if less-experienced teachers quickly go over course material, students may do worse on their post-tests than if they had access to experienced teachers who take the time to go over course content. While there is no perfect way to address differences in teacher preparedness between school districts, differences in course content have been addressed in prior studies by focusing on a specific financial education curriculum with “well-defined” and “standardized” content (Walstad et al., 2010).

With these estimation challenges in mind, let us now consider the findings of some of the existing literature on the relationship between financial education and financial literacy. As briefly discussed, each study has shortcomings and estimation challenges that they attempt to address, with varying degrees of success. Regardless, due to the volatility of human nature and economic research, the data from such studies is still important to consider when determining the relationship between financial education and financial literacy.

Empirical Literature Review

Now that the concepts of diminishing marginal returns and human interest have been introduced, along with common estimation challenges present in much of the existing literature, key papers attempting to study and measure the impact of financial education on financial literacy can be reviewed. For the sake of clarity, this paper will focus on reviewing findings related to high school students and data regarding students' prior knowledge and interest.

Mandell (2008) reviews the findings of the “2008 National Jump\$tart Coalition Survey of High School Seniors and College Students.” In cooperating high schools from around the country, the survey revealed that high school seniors who previously completed a course related to personal finance scored an average of 47.5 percent on the administered post-course exam, compared to the total average score of 48.3. However, in contrast, students who played a stock market game as part of the course scored around 6 percent better than the total average score (Mandell, 2008). With completing a course in personal finance taken to mean prior knowledge, the survey’s findings could support the theory of diminishing marginal returns – students with prior knowledge did worse on this post-course test than students with no prior knowledge. Additionally, they could also support the idea that interest in the topics learned could positively influence their test scores and, potentially, short-term financial literacy. However, there are several critical problems in this survey. The difference in data regarding prior knowledge is too small to be considered significant – less than 1.0 percent. Additionally, while Mandell is vigilant in separating data based on demographics such as sex, race, region of residence, and the like, he fails to account for differences between schools – he does not seem to greatly consider how differences in teacher preparation and specific financial education curriculums can impact differences between schools and student scores. Furthermore, Mandell simply uses a multiple-choice post-test and compares the data to that of previous years to compare findings. As we will see in other papers, this variety in knowledge evaluation will prove detrimental to research into financial education courses as a whole.

In comparison, Walstad et al. (2010) attempted to account for estimation challenges related to inter-school differences – in line with previous examples, course content and teacher preparation. In an attempt to control these challenges, Walstad et al. focused their research on a

specific curriculum, *Financing Your Future (FYF)*, and encouraged teachers to attend personal finance workshops hosted by groups affiliated with the Council for Economic Education to supplement their pre-course training. To control for demographic differences, Walstad et al. separated their findings based on categories such as gender, future educational plans, and class level – however, they did not separate findings by race or income, as studies such as Mandell’s had, which could potentially impact findings. Additionally, Walstad et al. measured their data using multiple-choice pre and post-tests, comparing data to a control group that did not participate in an FYF financial education course, which differs from studies such as Mandell’s that only used a post-test, without treatment or control groups. However, because some of the treatment and control groups attended the same school, there is also a chance that the treatment could have influenced the control group (with students across groups studying and sharing information), a factor that could prove problematic to the authenticity of Walstad et al.’s study. In a notable set of findings, after controlling for other factors, Walstad et al. ultimately found that students who owned their own credit cards exhibited greater gains (22.8) than those who did not (20.3), those who had only used their parents’ cards (15.2), and those who had used their own or their parents’ credit cards (15.9) (Walstad et al., 2010). Assuming that owning their own credit cards would bring about prior knowledge in students, these findings directly reject ideas of diminishing marginal returns regarding prior knowledge – in this case, students with prior knowledge experienced greater gains than those without. Instead, these findings potentially suggest the influence of human interest on financial literacy gains. Assuming that students with credit cards would be more likely to show interest and initiative in financial education, as they would personally benefit from financial knowledge, personal interest could impact gains from financial education more than prior knowledge, or lack thereof.

In the most recent key paper, Lusardi and Mitchell (2014) determined financial literacy gains from financial education courses by examining the lifelong behavior of students – rather than short-term test scores – and critiqued many past studies. This paper, unlike the two previous papers, does not offer new research of its own, but instead serves to establish a connection between numerous other key studies (all with their faults). As such, the aforementioned estimation challenges do not apply to this key paper specifically. However, in analyzing multiple previous studies, Lusardi and Mitchell found that financial literacy is greatly heterogeneous between demographic factors, from religion, race, and the like, making Walstad’s omission of race and income data all the more troubling (Lusardi & Mitchell, 2014). Furthermore, Lusardi and Mitchell also make a point to mention that less than one-fifth of K-12 educators (current and prospective) felt well-equipped to teach financial education courses – in part, due to many states not “providing or promoting” financial teacher training (Lusardi & Mitchell, 2014). Throughout their paper, they also emphasize that financial literacy is a lifelong necessity. In this way, key studies such as Mandell’s and Walstad’s are extremely limited in their utility, as they are largely limited to short-term effects and do not give information on long-term retention of financial education topics and the course’s impact on financial behavior later in life. Many issues are recurring within studies on the effectiveness of financial literacy – with this being the case, it seems unlikely that many past studies can ultimately provide legitimate data on the impact of financial education on financial literacy, especially concerning diminishing marginal returns and human interest.

However, Hathaway and Khatiwada (2008) provide a more optimistic outlook. Authors Hathaway and Khatiwada also evaluated past research – as such, while the aforementioned estimation challenges may apply to the studies they are critiquing, such challenges do not pertain

to this paper itself. Similarly to Lusardi and Mitchell, Hathaway and Khatiwada also view the impact of financial education on financial literacy through a long-term perspective, directly contrasting studies such as Mandell's and Walstad et al.'s that focus on short-term test scores. Based on several studies evaluating the financial habits of adults who underwent financial education in high school, Hathaway and Khatiwada found that school-based programs had limited success. Some studies reviewed found that adults who underwent high school financial education programs had greater rates of financial literacy (via saving and wealth accumulation) than those who did not, while other studies found that financially-educated students saved more in the short term. Other studies were not statistically significant and had no definitive findings at all (Hathaway & Khatiwada, 2008). However, ultimately, Hathaway and Khatiwada concluded that there is no conclusive evidence of financial education impacting financial literacy, regardless of diminishing marginal returns or human interest – either because the programs do not work, or because they are not being properly evaluated (Hathaway & Khatiwada, 2008).

Conclusion

After establishing three main estimation challenges prevalent in much of the existing literature and reviewing some key papers studying the relationship between financial education and financial literacy, much still remains unclear. Mandell (2008) potentially supports theories of diminishing marginal returns regarding prior knowledge and the importance of interest and behavior in the extent to which financial education influences financial literacy. In stark contrast, Walstad et al. (2010) found evidence supporting human interest and behavior to be of greater impact than diminishing marginal returns. However, both studies were rife with problematic factors and did not properly account for enough estimation challenges for their findings to be considered “accurate.” Coinciding with this critique, Lusardi and Mitchell (2014) emphasized

findings of differences in financial literacy between demographic groups and lack of teacher preparedness for teaching financial education courses, undermining both results of the two previous key studies. Hathaway and Khatiwada (2008) similarly concluded that while school-based programs reported limited success, evidence on the relationship between financial education and financial literacy is still inconclusive, and further research must be conducted. Specifically, they call for “formal program evaluation methods” (Hathaway & Khatiwada, 2008) to keep research consistent and estimation challenges to a minimum. As such, while many studies such as those of Mandell and Walstad et al. attempt to come to conclusions regarding the relationship between financial education and financial literacy, Lusardi and Mitchell and Hathaway and Khatiwada make excellent arguments for the inconclusiveness of present data. With so many estimation challenges and differences in data measurement present throughout studies, it is currently impossible to determine the full impact of diminishing marginal returns regarding prior knowledge and human interest on the relationship between financial education and financial literacy. For future research, following Hathaway and Khatiwada’s recommendations, researchers must create, or adhere to, specific and shared evaluation methods that allow for research to be more easily compared while keeping estimation challenges to a minimum. These methods could potentially include requiring data separation based on key demographic data (e.g. race, household income, etc.), measurement of both short- and long-term effects, and pre-course financial education workshops for teachers to ensure similar quality. However, given my analysis of present key studies, it is still currently unknown what the impact of such education on students’ financial literacy will be, especially regarding Minnesota’s recent policy.

References

- Abrams, S. (2023, February 15). *House DFL proposes school funding formula hike that would boost K-12 spending by over \$1 billion*. House DFL proposes school funding formula hike that would boost K-12 spending by over \$1 billion - Session Daily - Minnesota House of Representatives. <https://www.house.mn.gov/SessionDaily/Story/17673>
- Abrams, S. (2023b, May 16). *House passes K-12 Education Bill that features \$2.2 billion funding boost, contentious policy changes*. House passes K-12 education bill that features \$2.2 billion funding boost, contentious policy changes - Session Daily - Minnesota House of Representatives. <https://www.house.mn.gov/sessiondaily/Story/18009>
- Driscoll, D., Halcoussis, D., & Svorny, S. (2008). Gains in standardized test scores: Evidence of diminishing returns to achievement. *Economics of Education Review*, 27(2), 211–220. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.econedurev.2006.10.002>
- Einhorn, E., & Chiwaya, N. (2020, August 31). *How Minneapolis re-segregated its schools and set the stage for a national crisis*. NBCNews.com. <https://www.nbcnews.com/specials/minneapolis-re-segregated-schools-set-the-stage-national-crisis/#:~:text=In%20the%201993%2D94%20school,National%20Center%20for%20Education%20Statistics>
- Faircloth, R. (2023, June 21). *Minnesota's new graduation requirements: Learn how to manage money and participate in democracy*. Star Tribune. <https://www.startribune.com/goal-for-new-minnesota-high-school-graduates-better-citizens-who-dont-fritter-away-their-money/600284203/>

Griffith, M. (2023, April 21). *House passes massive K-12 Education Funding, policy package.*

Minnesota Reformer.

<https://minnesotareformer.com/2023/04/20/house-on-the-verge-of-passing-massive-k-12-education-funding-policy-package/>

Hathaway, I., & Khatiwada, S. (2008). Do financial education programs work? *Working Paper*

(Federal Reserve Bank of Cleveland). <https://doi.org/10.26509/frbc-wp-200803>

Kim, P. (2023, November 30). *States with the best and Worst Credit scores in 2023.* Business

Insider.

<https://www.businessinsider.com/personal-finance/states-with-best-worst-credit-scores#:~:text=The%20average%20Minnesota%20resident%20has,score%20is%20Mississippi%20C%20at%20680>

Lusardi, A., & Mitchell, O. S. (2014). The economic importance of Financial Literacy: Theory and Evidence. *Journal of Economic Literature*, 52(1), 5–44.

<https://doi.org/10.1257/jel.52.1.5>

Macht, C. (2020, June). *Minnesota economic disparities by race and origin.* Minnesota

Disparities by Race Report.

https://mn.gov/deed/assets/061020_MN_disparities_final_tcm1045-435939.pdf

Mandell, L. (2008). *The Financial Literacy of Young American adults.* 2008 JumpStart Financial Literacy Survey.

<https://views.smgww.org/assets/pdf/2008%20JumpStart%20Financial%20Literacy%20Survey.pdf>

Schoenberg, K. (2022, March 7). *Special education and El Cross Subsidy*. MREA.

<https://www.mreavoice.org/special-education-and-el-cross-subsidy/#:~:text=The%20cross%20subsidy%20is%20the,a%20district%27s%20general%20fund%20greatly>

Severson, G. (2023, March 1). *Minnesota bill would require personal finance class for all high school ...* KARE 11.

<https://www.kare11.com/article/news/local/breaking-the-news/minnesota-bill-require-personal-finance-class-for-all-high-school-students-to-graduate/89-8138a031-6e63-4bde-946e-860978dc263d>

Sullivan, B. (2000, October 6). *HIGHLIGHTS OF STATE EDUCATION POLICES FROM 1970-2000*. Minnesota Government.

<https://mn.gov/mnddc/past/pdf/00s/00/00-HSE-MDE.pdf>

What does Minnesota's student debt look like? Minnesota Education Equity Partnership. (2023, August 2).

<https://www.mneep.org/2023/08/02/what-does-minnesotas-student-debt-look-like/#:~:text=Their%20average%20debt%20at%20graduation,Institute%20for%20College%20Access%20%26%20Success>

2022-2023 NGPF's 2023 State of Financial Education Report. NGPF. (2023, March).

https://d3f7q2msm2165u.cloudfront.net/aaa-content/user/files/Files/NGPF_AnnualReport_2023.pdf

U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, Children's Bureau. (1998). *Child Maltreatment 1996: Reports From the States to the National Child Abuse and Neglect Data System*. Washington, DC: U.S. Government Printing Office.

- U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, Administration on Children, Youth and Families. (2007). *Child Maltreatment 2005*. Washington, DC: U.S. Government Printing Office.
- Varcoe, K., Martin, A., Devitto, Z., & Go, C. (2013, April 23). *Using a financial education curriculum for Teens*. SSRN. <https://ssrn.com/abstract=2255109>
- Walstad, W. B., Rebeck, K., & MacDonald, R. A. (2010). The effects of financial education on the financial knowledge of high school students. *Journal of Consumer Affairs, 44*(2), 336–357. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1745-6606.2010.01172.x>
- Zapp, D. (2019). *Money Matters on Campus*. EVERFI. <https://everfi.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/05/MoneyMatters-2019.pdf>.